

**SYNTACTIC AND SEMANTIC FEATURES OF COMPARISON IN ENGLISH,
UZBEK AND RUSSIAN.**

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Abstract: As we know Comparative typology is an important branch of linguistics and this is a crucial factor when comparing. This article is about the semantic characteristics of synonyms of English, Russian and English languages

Keywords: Comparative synonymy, syntactical connection, position of the elements ,dominational phrase, syntactical classifications.

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Comparative synonymy that dealt with comparing of language units and languages that did not share common root language played an important role in the emerging and developing of the subject. Comparison of structural languages that were not substantial also was crucial in the development of Comparative synonymy. A sentence is an integral unit of speech having a communicative purpose; it expresses a statement, a question or inducement. The sentence expresses predication, i.e. shows whether the event is real or unreal, desirable or obligatory, stated as truth or asked about, etc. The sentence can consist of one or several notional words. In Uzbek the sentence is characterized as a smallest communicative unit with the following features: It has predication which consists of modality and time. It may have the meanings of person and number. It is addressed to a hearer. It has a new information. It has the speaker's intention. It is related to certain speech situation. It has definite intonation. Phrases and sentences are universal linguistic phenomena. Their structures can be used as a basis for typological comparison. For identifying the type of a phrase, the following criteria have been established: a) The type of syntactical connection in a phrase. b) The means of expressing the syntactical connection. c) The position of the elements of the phrase. The elements of a phrase can be syntactically equal or unequal. In the former case, neither of the elements modifies the other. We can change their position without any change of meaning. Such combinations are called equipotent. e.g. father and son; son and father. If the elements are syntactically unequal, one of them modifies the other.

The principal element is called the “kernel” or “head word”. The subordinate element is called “the adjunct”. Their respective positions are different for different types of phrases and different languages. Such phrases are called dominational. The connections between the elements of a dominational phrase can be further grouped into: the combination of a noun with its attribute expressed by an adjective or a noun the combination of a verb with a subordinate element expressed by a noun, pronoun or a verbal the combination of a verb and an adverbial modifier or the combination of an adjective or an adverb and the subordinate element expressed by an adverb e.g. the train arrived e.g. an emerald ring; a woman of strong character e.g. to read the book; to read it; to decide to stay e.g. to talk quickly; extremely quick; extremely quickly according to Greenberg’s classification, the English and Russian languages belong to the group having prepositions, adjectives in preposition to nouns and word order. But Uzbek language belongs to an inflectional group of languages and word order. At the same time, the facts of the languages show that these languages are not identical in their syntactical structure. There is evidently need for more subtle syntactical classifications. Additionally, as a similarity can be considered the following characteristics like in all three languages there are two or more subjects and predicates in the compound and complex sentences. Two or more sentences in compound sentences are combined with coordinative conjunctions in compared languages (and, but, or, и, но, или, лекин, ва, ёки). While in the complex sentence two or more sentences are combined with subordinate conjunctions in all three languages (if, because, если, потому что, агар, чунки) observed in English interrogative pronouns can make a subordinate sentence. But in Uzbek, such sentences are considered as simple ones (A scientist is a person who studies a lot. Олим кўп уқийдиган киши). Distinctively, in the English language in the unreal conditionals, plural form of verbs is used for both singular and plural subjects. But Russian and Uzbek languages don’t have such phenomenon. Thus another number of brief differences in syntactic level also can be listed in comparison of sentences of compared languages: Russian and Uzbek sentences are longer than English ones, Russians and Uzbeks are fond of long and colorful phrases while the English text is composed of comparatively short sentences, it is “ethical” to use short words and brief structures. In translation, Russian and Uzbek sentences can be divided into 2-3 short ones. The order of words in a sentence plays a great semantic role, the most important word stands at the beginning. E.g.: Russian - Вам этого не понять. Этого вам не понять. Uzbek - Сиз буни тушуна олмайсиз Буни сиз тушуна олмайсиз In English the word order is fixed, semantic shades of meaning are expressed by other means. In English, there can be one variant but with different intonation: You won’t understand this. Conclusion. Generally, there can be

observed differences, similarities and distinctive features in the deep comparative analysis of the types above. Such as compound- complex features are typical only for English and Uzbek languages and cannot be found in Russian. Or else Russian and Uzbek have syndetic and asyndetic features of dividing sentences into types while English has another criterion for this.

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